

6. R. C. AGGARWAL, D. S. S. VARAPRASADA RAO and V. C. SEKHAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 622.
7. C. LORENZINI, C. PELIZZI, G. PELIZZI and G. PREDIERI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton, Trans.*, 1983, 721.
8. S. C. JACKELS, K. FARMERY, E. K. BAREFIELD, N. J. ROSE and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 2893; A. M. TAIT and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, 16, 966.
9. W. J. GRAY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1977, 7, 81.
10. A. M. FISHER and R. C. STOUFFER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1172.
11. G. J. O'CONNOR, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, 29, 204.

bases (1a-d) derived from 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and 4-substituted anilines.

- 1a, X=H (Ahmcanil)
 1b, X=Me (4-Me-Ahmcanil)
 1c, X=Cl (4-Cl-Ahmcanil)
 1d, X=NO₂ (4-NO₂-Ahmcanil)

Formation Constants of Lanthanide(III) Complexes with 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin Anils

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Experimental

The Schiff bases (1a-d) were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (Ahmc) and aniline itself, or 4-methyl-, 4-chloro- and 4-nitro-aniline as the case may be in methanol for 30 min. The resulting orange-yellow crystals that separated on cooling were filtered, washed with aqueous 5% ethanol and finally recrystallised from methanol (Table 1).

IN continuation of earlier studies^{1,2} on the coordinating tendencies of coumarin and Schiff bases with the metal ions, I report here the formation constants of lanthanide(III) complexes with the Schiff

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)*			ν _{OH}	ν _{C=O}	ν _{C=N}
		O	H	N			
1a	191	73.8 (73.7)	4.9 (5.1)	4.5 (4.7)	3 280-3 380	1 720	1 610
1b	209	74.0 (74.2)	5.2 (5.5)	4.3 (4.5)	3 020-3 100	1 730	1 605
1c	202	65.6 (65.9)	4.0 (4.2)	4.0 (4.2)	3 010-3 090	1 720	1 600
1d	227	63.5 (63.9)	3.9 (4.1)	8.0 (8.2)	3 040-3 095	1 725	1 610

*Compd. 1c analysis : Found Cl, 10.6. Calcd. 10.8%.

TABLE 2—PROTON-LIGAND AND LANTHANIDE(III)-LIGAND CONSTANTS WITH Ahmcanil, Me-Ahmcanil, Cl-Ahmcanil and NO₂-Ahmcanil

Temp.=30°, Dioxane - Water=70% (v/v), I=0.1 M (NaClO₄)

	La	Ce	Pr	Nd	Sm	Gd	Dy
(a) Ahmcanil (pK _{OH} =8.50 and pK _{NH} =11.81)							
log β ₁	5.44	5.60	5.69	5.82	6.02	6.00	6.05
log β ₂	9.40	10.12	10.10	11.00	12.10	11.50	12.26
log β ₃	14.01	14.89	14.85	16.00	17.30	16.51	16.85
(b) Me-Ahmcanil (pK _{OH} =8.43 and pK _{NH} =11.72)							
log β ₁	5.80	6.20	6.41	6.41	6.80	6.61	6.85
log β ₂	10.70	11.45	11.81	11.54	12.71	12.01	12.70
log β ₃	15.05	15.50	15.16	15.34	17.60	16.49	17.00
(c) Cl-Ahmcanil (pK _{OH} =5.87)							
log β ₁	4.61	4.77	4.81	5.01	5.71	5.60	5.80
log β ₂	8.75	9.10	9.00	9.02	10.10	9.92	10.00
log β ₃	10.55	13.34	13.16	13.70	14.60	14.24	14.00
(d) NO ₂ -Ahmcanil (pK _{OH} =5.71)							
log β ₁	4.52	4.74	4.72	4.91	5.41	5.80	5.60
log β ₂	7.85	8.41	8.30	8.52	9.20	8.93	9.04
log β ₃	10.01	11.00	11.20	12.00	13.00	12.10	12.81

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants (Table 2) with trivalent La, Pr, Ce, Nd, Sm, Gd and Dy were determined by Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique^{3,4}. The ligands **1a** and **1b** showed two buffer regions, one in acid medium (pH 4-5) and the other in basic medium (pH 6.5-8) corresponding to the release of protons of phenolic OH and azomethine ($-\overset{+}{C}=\text{NH}-$) groups, respectively. Ligands **1c** and **1d** showed only one buffer region (pH 7.5-8) corresponding to the release of phenolic proton which can be traced to the electron-withdrawing effect of Cl and NO₂ groups. The stability constants of lanthanide(III) complexes are almost in the increasing order of their Z^2/r values, suggesting that lanthanum(III)-ligand interaction to be primarily ionic. With respect to the ligands the stability order is **1b** > **1a** > Ahmc > **1c** > **1d** in accordance with relative basicities of ligands. Plots of $\log K_1$ ($\log \beta_1$) vs $\log K_{\text{OH}}^{\text{H}}$ of these ligands are linear for each metal-ligand system.

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References

1. P. SINGH and G. P. POKHARIYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 753.
2. G. P. POKHARIYAL, *J. Inst. Chem. (Calcutta)*, communicated.
3. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3396; 1954, 2904.
4. G. P. POKHARIYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 400.

The Influence of Thiourea on Gallium(III) Ion Reduction on DME

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IN most electrolytes, gallium(III) ions reduce on DME producing badly formed irreversible polarographic waves with maximum¹. The process is catalysed by thiocyanate and azide ions and also by an increase of the ionic strength of the solution^{2,3}. Some uni- and poly-valent anions and cations suppress the polarographic maximum and influence on the kinetics of electrode reaction of gallium(III)^{4,5}.

In our studies on the influence of surface active substances on Ga^{III} ions on DME we observed that the presence of thiourea (TU) in the solution affects the electrode process. Our aim in the present

study was to determine the changes in the kinetics and mechanism of Ga^{III} ion reduction on DME under the influence of TU. The investigation was carried out in two kinds of electrolytes: 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ and 3.3 mol dm⁻³ NaSCN.

Experimental

The measurements were carried out in three-electrode system (DME, SCE, Hg pool) using dc and square wave polarography. In the latter method a Radelkis OH-104 polarograph was used. In order to obtain more accurate results of dc polarograph a system of a potentiostat, a linear sweep generator and a Aritma BAK 4T X-Y recorder was used. The rate of flow of the capillary was $m=2.61 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$; drop time $t=2.9 \text{ s}$ in 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ solution with height of mercury column $h=1.085 \text{ m}$.

The Ga^{III} solutions were obtained from 4 N Ga(NO₃)₃ (International Enzymes Limited, England) by dissolving it in dilute HClO₄.

Gallium concentration was kept constant throughout the investigation at $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. Thiourea, NaClO₄ and NaSCN solutions were prepared from analytically pure salts. The pH levels in NaClO₄ and NaSCN solutions were kept constant (2.1 and 3.3, respectively). At such pH levels the hydrogen wave did not interfere with Ga^{III} ion reduction and no gallium hydroxide precipitation took place². The concentration of thiourea varied from 10^{-4} to $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The measurements were carried out in an argon atmosphere at 25°. One series of measurements involved an addition of gelatine (0.002%). Water and mercury employed were distilled twice.

Results and Discussion

Influence of TU on Ga^{III} ion reduction in 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄ solution, pH=2.1: It follows from the results that the increasing TU concentration increases the limiting current of the electrode reaction of reduction of Ga^{III} ions on DME and as well the half-wave potential of the electrode process shifts towards positive potential. Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of Ga^{III} were applied⁶. These indicated the irreversible and diffusion nature of the reduction of Ga^{III} ions in 6.0 mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄. Under such conditions gallium-thiourea complexes undergo reduction on DME and they are more electroactive than the aquo-Ga^{III} ions. The latter is suggested by the direction of half-wave potential shift. The maximum coordination number of the complexes calculated by the method of Lingane, is approximately $j=4$. Addition of gelatine to the solution produces no significant changes. This seems to point out to the formation of gallium-thiourea complexes inside the solution as blocking of the electrode surface by gelatine does not affect their formation.